

**THE THEORY OF FERDINAND DE SAUSSURE AND HIS
LINGUOTERMINOSYSTEM IN THE LATE XIX - EARLY XX CENTURY.
FORMATION OF THE LINGUISTIC TERMINOLOGICAL SYSTEM.**

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Abstract. *In this article the information is given about the theory of Ferdinand de Saussure and his linguoterminosystem in the late XIX - early XX century as well as formation of the linguistic terminological system. The article also clarifies the importance of linguoterminosystem in linguistics. And there are given some researches about the linguistic terminological systems.*

Keywords: *Semiotics, semicolons, human sciences, interpretations, conventional, functional, fricatives, central tenets, incorporated.*

It arose due to the growing need to facilitate content, communication and translation, as well as to understand the concept of users belonging to different communities but with similar common knowledge. According to researchers Silvia Pavel and Diane Nolet¹, the term terminology means “the specific language of science, art, literature, or social organization,” such as agricultural content or tourism content. Additionally, the term narrowly means “a linguistic discipline devoted to the study of concepts and terms used in a particular language.” It should be noted here that the universal language is the language used in daily life, while the specific language is based on certain concepts and language usage and is used to facilitate communication in certain information.

Ferdinand de Saussure was a Swiss linguist, semiotician and philosopher. His ideas formed the basis of many important developments in linguistics and semiotics in the 20th century. He is widely considered one of the founders of 20th-century linguistics and one of the two founders of semiotics (or what Saussure called semiotics). Roy Harris, one of his translators, noted Saussure's contributions to language and “to all subjects in the human sciences.” Especially in linguistics, philosophy, psychoanalysis, psychology, sociology and anthropology. Although it has become more detailed and criticized over time, the organizational dimensions introduced by Saussure continue to inform modern methods of studying language. As Leonard Bloomfield said after reviewing the course: “This gives us a theoretical basis for the study of human language.”

Saussure's theoretical reconstruction of the sound system of the Proto-Indo-European language, especially his laryngeal theory, was unsubstantiated at the time, but after the decipherment of Hittite it was widely used by later linguists such as Emile Benveniste. The and the writings of Émile Benveniste. Walter Couvreur Both were directly inspired by reading the 1878 Memoirs.

Saussure had a great influence on the development of language theory in the first half of the 20th century, and his points became among the main points in the structure of words. His main contribution to design is his theory of the two-level reality of language. The first is language, which is an abstract and abstract process, and the second is speech, which refers to the real words we hear in real life. This framework was later adopted by Claude Lévi-Strauss, who used a two-level model to determine the veracity of myths. His idea is that all fairy tales have an underlying structure that creates the patterns that make up their stories.

The most important work done in Europe after Saussure's death was done by the Prague School. Most importantly, in the decade from 1940, Nikolay Trubetzkoy and Roman Jakobson

led the Prague School to create a course on phonological theory. Jakobson's generalized theory of phonological function as a hierarchy of notes with certain properties is the first good school of phonology. Solutions of the language analysis plane according to Saussure's propositions. Elsewhere, Louis Hjelmslev and the Copenhagen School proposed a new interpretation from a structuralist theoretical framework.

In the United States, the term "structuralism" has become vague, and Saussure's ideas influenced Leonard Bloomfield's classification, but its influence remains limited. Systemic functional linguistics is a theory that should be firmly based on Saussure's semiotic concepts, albeit with some modifications. Ruqaiya Hasan describes the study of linguistics as a "post-Saussurean" theory of language. Michael Halliday believes that:

Saussure uses symbols as an organizational concept of language structure and uses this to express the agreement of language, that is, the word "l'arbitration". The result of this is to show one of the decisions of the body, which is the voice of the individual, thus making it clearer that the rest are not arbitrary. A clear example of a nonspecific case is the way different types of meaning in a language are expressed by different grammatical structures, as when linguistic structures are defined as the study of content.

Saussure's most important work, *Studies in General Linguistics*, was written by his former students Charles Bally and Albert Sechehaye and recorded in Saussure's lectures in Geneva, published in 1916. Work has become one of the most influential words of the 20th century. not because of the content, but because of Saussure's new method of discussing linguistic facts.

What he really wants to emphasize is that language can be analyzed as a set of different concepts, apart from the specific features of production and rapid comprehension. Examples of these concepts include the concept of speech signals, which consist of signs and symbols. Although the sign also has a referent, Saussure believed that this was beyond the imagination of the interpreter. Article "Language is a system of symbols for expressing thought." A science that studies symbolic life in society and is part of the social and psychological field. Saussure believes that semiotics deals with everything that can be used as a symbol, and he calls this semiotics.

While still a student, Saussure published an important work on Proto-Indo-European; here he explained a strange language based on the principles of missing numbers, which he called "articulation coefficients". Scandinavian researcher Hermann Moller suggested that these might be consonants, leading to what is now known as the laryngeal theory. After the Hittite text was discovered and deciphered, Polish linguist Jerzy Kuryłowicz confirmed this theory by confirming that Hittite consonants were in the position of lost phonemes that Saussure had considered some 48 years earlier. It has been suggested that Saussure's work on this subject encouraged the development of his system by making words illegal by introducing phonemes that were unknown at the time.

It is generally accepted that the greatest achievement of nineteenth-century English studies was the development of the comparative method, consisting of phonological systems, grammar, and the linguistic structure of the language. will be compared systematically. Instruction on vocabulary and "family tree". Just as French, Italian, Portuguese, Romanian, Spanish, and other Romance languages evolved from Latin, Latin, Greek, and Sanskrit, as well as many other European languages and the Celtic, Germanic, and Slavic languages of Asia, also evolved from Latin. It also evolved from Latin. Some ancient languages are now commonly

known as Indo-European or Proto-Indo-European. It has been known for centuries that all Romance languages are derived from Latin and thus form a "family". However, the existence of Indo-European languages and the nature of their genetic relationships were first discovered by comparative linguists in the 19th century.

The main impetus for the development of comparative languages came at the end of the 18th century, when it was discovered that Sanskrit had many similarities with Greek and Latin. Although British orientalist Sir William Jones was not the first to notice the similarities, he is credited with bringing them to scholars, and in 1786 he suggested that all three languages "must be from somewhere, but this will no longer exist." By this time many texts and descriptions of the ancient Germanic languages had been published, and Jones realized that Germanic, Old Persian, and even Celtic languages had evolved from the same "source."

The next important step came in 1822, when the German scholar Jacob Grimm, following the Danish linguist Rasmus Rask, pointed out in the second edition of his comparative grammar of Germanic that there were a number of systematic correspondences between the sounds of Germanic and the sounds of Greek, Latin, and Sanskrit in related words. Grimm noted, for example, that where Gothic had an *f*, Latin, Greek, and Sanskrit frequently had a *p* (e.g., Gothic *fotus*, Latin *pedis*, Greek *podós*, Sanskrit *padás*, all meaning "foot"); when Gothic had a *p*, the non-Germanic languages had a *b*; when Gothic had a *b*, the non-Germanic languages had what Grimm called an "aspirate". In order to account for these correspondences he postulated a cyclical "soundshift" in the prehistory of Germanic, in which the original "aspirates" became voiced unaspirated stops, the original voiced unaspirated stops became voiceless, and the original voiceless stops became "aspirates". Grimm's term, "aspirate," it will be noted, covered such phonetically distinct categories as aspirated stops, produced with an accompanying audible puff of breath, and fricatives, produced with audible friction as a result of incomplete closure in the vocal tract.

In the work of the next 50 years the idea of sound change was made more precise, and, in the 1870s, a group of scholars known collectively as the Junggrammatiker ("young grammarians," or Neogrammarians) put forward the thesis that all changes in the sound system of a language as it developed through time were subject to the operation of regular sound laws. The thesis that laws are fixed in their operation (unless they are specifically affected by the comparative effect) came to be seen as quite appropriately inconsistent, but by the end of the 19th century it had become generally accepted and a source of debate. Using principles of continuous sound change, researchers are able to reconstruct "ancestral" information and then derive it from information found in a language. This copy of the meeting is marked with an asterisk in the file. Thus, from the Reconstructed Proto-Indo-European word **dekm* for ten, Sanskrit *daśa*, Greek *déka*, Latin *decem* can be derived from several different sound rules thought to operate independently in many languages and Gothic *taihun*. A branch of the Indo-European language family. The problem of sound change is discussed in more detail in the Diachronic Linguistics section.

The analogy seems to be said in connection with the regulation of the voice in certain situations preventing its normal functioning. This is the thought of the neogrammarists. But it can be recognized that in the 20th century metaphors, in the best sense, sometimes played a more important role in the development of language than simply preventing the normal rules from changing. Phonetic system of the language. When learning to speak, the child likes to manipulate unusual or irregular information by comparing it with established and structured language. For

example, "came" instead of "come", "black" instead of "water", etc. will prefer to say, like "love" etc. like he said. The fact that the child does this proves that he or she has learned the patterns or rules of his or her language. He will continue to "forget" some examples and replace them with negative letters popular in the speech of the previous generation. But sometimes he will choose a "new" form of the metaphor (e.g. "black" instead of "rounded") and this will become a recognized and accepted form.

Today, terminology is part of applied linguistics, a science that includes lexicography, translation, writing and language teaching. It is worth noting here that the four areas of professional speech are associated with: translation requires knowledge of special languages bilingual or multilingual; writing involves the use of these terms in monolingual speech; and Professional language teaching aimed at student acquisition. ; The organizational practice of comparing concepts and their meanings occurs in the context of interpretation.

In short, please remember that the study of terminology requires many skills:

- Being able to identify elements that represent an author's idea;
- Ability to determine the use of content in relevant documents. ;
- Conciseness The ability to clearly describe and explain content; Article
- Ability to approve or opt-out of certain uses to encourage open communication.

According to research conducted on many languages, the word "time" can be explained and interpreted differently. For example, A. Reformatsky defines time as follows: "Time is a special word"⁴. AV Kalinin calls some concepts "special words" and divides them into two groups:

- 1) Special words, first of all, have content.
- 2) Special words as well as content include expertise.

Also A.V. Kalinin distinguishes between terminology and professionalism:

"The difference between terminology and professionalism is that a word is the expression or name of a completely official, accepted and legitimized idea in a specific field of science, business, agriculture or technology" "Professionalism, on the other hand, is business, "It is a semi-official word meaning business, often spoken as a living language. In fact, the concept is not fixed but scientific interpretation."

H. Jamolkhanov analyzed this word and wrote: "The term is a noun representing specific ideas in science, technology, literature, art and other industries and is used only in a specific field. For example: calabash - suvkovoq, thrush - o' simlikyarasi (in agriculture); rectangle, square (geometry); 6

It is the "authentic" character that should be emphasized, showing the feature of the subject, ensuring the accuracy of the meaning and its consistency with the words.

In general, accuracy and integrity of speech reflect the science, education and culture of the country. The development and prescription of the language used varies between different studies and depends on the progress of a study. Since this development is not affected, the appearance and specificity of the new content will not be affected either.

In general, it is important to carefully define and prepare language content in textbooks and manuals, as in traditional courses. Lack of detail and standardization of terminology also affects the speaking style.

Terminology is used as a type of communication skill to express understanding of reality. According to Vinogradov, "The creation and interpretation of concepts has two aspects, two

perspectives: the structure of language and understanding and the development of semantic methods for understanding science."

D.S. Lotte mentions a list of words that can be cut: weapons, tools, elements, etc.); objects; mathematical concepts (no., geometric shapes) etc.); unit of measurement." Kalinin tries to separate this word from the word profession as follows: "Time is purely formal in a certain science, business, agriculture, technology, it is an expression. A recognition is the name of the concept of legitimacy, however, if the word profession is used as profession, it is a semi-official word that frequently circulates among professions in the language of life."

In fact, by examining various classifications,

- 1) Clarity, or at least a clear preference;
- 2) Semantic accuracy;
- 3) Simplicity;
- 4) Neutral style, no expression 45, 4) 4, 4) Relationship with other elements;
- 6) Nominative;
- 7) International;
- 8) Using the word alone, i.e. ability to use out of context.

Therefore, the word appears not only in the lexical system of words, but also in the conceptual system of a special science, that is, time is devoted to a scientific discipline, for example: phoneme - a linguistic word, Synecdocha - a style, written language.

REFERENCES

1. Bergenholtz, H.,Tarp, S. 1995. "Manual of specialised lexicography". John Benjamins Publishing Company.
2. Klasson K. Developments in the Terminology of Physics and Technology. Stockolm, 1977.
3. Terminology: Theory and Method. Edined by O. Akhmanova and G. Agapova. M.: Moscow State University, 1974. - 205 p.
4. Даниленко В.П. Актуальные направления лингвистического исследования русской терминологии // Современные проблемы русской терминологии. -М., 1986.— С. 10-21.
5. Даниленко В.П. Русская терминология: Опыт лингвистического описания. М.: Наука, 1977. — 246 с.
6. Лотте Д.С. Основы построения научно-технической терминологии. Вопросы теории и методики. — М.: Изд-во АН СССР, 1961.- 158 с.
7. Кубрякова Е.С. О современном понимании термина «концепт» влингвистике и культурологии // Реальность, язык и сознание: Междунар.меж-вуз. сб. науч. тр. Тамбов, 2002
8. Реформатский А.А. Что такое термин и терминология // Вопросы терминологии. Материалы Всесоюзного терминологического совещания. М.: Изд-во Акад. Наук СССР, 1961. - С. 46-54.